

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D3.2 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable is the second version of the Transformative Pathway Roadmap, presenting updates on the integration of UP2030 solutions in the UP2030 cities.</p> <p>The goal of this deliverable is twofold: i) to serve as a practical guide for project stakeholders, including cities and liaisons, interested in reviewing the available solutions and their implementation in city prototypes, and ii) to provide a technical overview of the tools' status as they move towards integration.</p> <p>Each UP2030 solution is presented in a dedicated section that includes a short description and its objectives. Additionally, the city prototypes are outlined, highlighting the cities vision, the specific challenges each city aims to address, and the tools mapped to achieve this vision. Finally, an overview of the integration and interoperability plan is provided, including milestones, timelines, and potential updates.</p> <p>The Transformative Pathways Roadmap is a living document, with information updated as the UP2030 project progresses and when significant changes occur. It builds on D3.1 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 1, and an updated final version will be delivered in M36.</p>			

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Executive summary

This deliverable is the second version of the Transformative Pathway Roadmap, presenting updates on the integration of UP2030 solutions in the UP2030 cities.

The goal of this deliverable is twofold: i) to serve as a practical guide for project stakeholders, including cities and liaisons, interested in reviewing the available solutions and their implementation in city prototypes, and ii) to provide a technical overview of the tools' status as they move towards integration.

Each UP2030 solution is presented in a dedicated section that includes a short description and its objectives. Additionally, the city prototypes are outlined, highlighting the cities vision, the specific challenges each city aims to address, and the tools mapped to achieve this vision. Finally, an overview of the integration and interoperability plan is provided, including milestones, timelines, and potential updates.

The Transformative Pathways Roadmap is a living document, with information updated as the UP2030 project progresses and when significant changes occur. It builds on D3.1 – “Transformative pathway roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 1”, and an updated final version will be delivered in M36.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package (WP) structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with WP3 leaders and tasks leaders. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D3.1 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 1</p> <p>D3.4 – Bundle of digital twins tools for net zero decision-making 1</p> <p>D3.6 – Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 1</p> <p>D3.8 – Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 1</p> <p>D4.2 – UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities 2</p> <p>D4.3 – Sustained engagement strategy of Learning & Action Alliances to promote the neutrality vision in the UP2030 pilots</p>	<p>D3.3 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 3</p> <p>D3.5 – Bundle of digital twins tools for net zero decision-making 2</p> <p>D3.7 – Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 2</p> <p>D3.9 – Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 2</p>

<p>Mil.7 - Cities establish user stories</p> <p>Mil.10 - Cities run third workshop on action</p>	<p>Mil.13 - All cities have at least one successful prototype</p>
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This deliverable, developed during M24 of the project, provides an extensive list of the available services/tools in the project, an overview of the cities Prototypes at this stage of the project and a shared understanding of the overall technological roadmap required for integrating UP2030 solutions within the UP2030 cities. The document is intended to primarily be shared with the directly involved partners, and subsequently with the entire consortium by distributing it via the UP2030 shared folder. Furthermore, given the public dissemination level of the document, extra third-party stakeholders seeking to benefit from UP2030's solutions and their technological roadmap could find the document advantageous as they could potentially benefit from UP2030's solutions and their technological roadmap. For instance, city planners, policymakers, and researchers could utilize the offered tools or leverage the insights to inform their urban development strategies, enhance decision-making processes, and foster collaborations for sustainable urban transformations.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
BH	Buro Happold
BIM	Building Information Model
CA	Circularity Assessment
CERTH	Centre for Research & Technology, Hellas
CIRCE	Fundación Circe Centro De Investigación De Recursos Y Consumos Energéticos
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CRCTool	Climate Resilient City Tool
CRF	City Resilience Framework
CV	Citizen Voice
CYFUD	Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design Method
D	Deliverable
DC	Design Clips
DCAP	District Climate Action Plan
DDSS	Draxis Decision Support System
DLCA	Dynamic Life Cycle Assessment
DT	Digital Twin
ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
GEM	Green Economy Model
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
ICA	I-Catalist
InVEST	Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs

IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC AR6	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) of its sixth assessment report cycle (AR6).
ISOCARP	ISOCARP Institute – Centre for Urban Excellence
JRL	Justice Readiness Level
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAA	Learning and Action Alliances
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LINKS	Fondazione LINKS
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional De Engenharia Civil
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry
MAG	Gruppo Maggioli
MCDA	Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis
METU	Middle East Technical University
MFA	Material and Flows Analysis
MfC	Mapping For Change
Mil	Milestone
NSM	Neutrality Story Map
P-GIS	Participatory Geographic Information System
PV	Photovoltaic
RAF	Resilience Assessment Framework
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
RCM	Regional Climate Model
SD	System Dynamics
SJBT	Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool

SJCM	Spatial Justice Conceptual Model
SJH	Spatial Justice Handbook
SJR	Spatial Justice Rubric
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TUD	Technische Universiteit Delft
UBTEM	Urban Building/Transport Energy Model
UCAM	University Of Cambridge
UCCRN	Urban Climate Change Research Network - European Hub
UDCW	Urban Design Climate Workshops
UHI	Urban Heat Island
VM	Vesela Motika
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The Transformative Pathways Roadmap focuses on aligning solution providers with city needs, integrating solutions into urban planning, adapting them to local contexts, and driving digital transitions toward climate neutrality. Its integration plan supports ongoing matchmaking between cities and services, coordinates the co-development and adaptation of solutions, and monitors their technical readiness. It also ensures interoperability, enabling seamless data exchange among different solutions.

The purpose of this deliverable, developed in Month 24 (M24) of the project, is twofold: i) to serve as a practical guide for project stakeholders, including cities and liaisons, interested in reviewing the available solutions and their implementation in city prototypes, and ii) to provide a technical overview of the tools' status as they move towards integration.

Deliverable 3.2 (D3.2) – “Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2” is a continuation of [D3.1 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 1](#) (Kalogiannis & Karakostas, 2023). While D3.1 focusses on the technical specifications of the tools/solutions, D3.2 is focusing on providing an overview of the available solutions and their current state (to further encourage city-solutions mapping) and briefly presenting the cities' prototypes (as formed at this stage of the project). D3.3 – “Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 3”, to be developed by M36, will focus into the cities' prototypes on their final stage. Together, D3.1, D3.2, and D3.3 create a cohesive narrative, acting as a storytelling journey of the technological roadmap of UP2030.

The deliverable is particularly beneficial for liaison partners and task leaders who are directly involved in the integration process. It serves as a foundation for guiding their efforts and ensuring a smooth implementation of the UP2030 solutions. While initially intended for the directly involved partners, the document will be shared with the entire consortium by distributing it through the UP2030 shared folder, and through the project's Zenodo¹ and Cordis² page. This ensures that all stakeholders within the consortium are well-informed and have access to the information outlined in the deliverable, as well as external viewers who wish to have further insights on what has been done regarding the integration of the solutions in UP2030.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure.
- ❖ Section 2 – UP2030 solutions – A practical guide: provides an extensive list of the solutions, including their description and objectives, provided by the tool providers.
- ❖ Section 3 – UP2030 solutions – Implementation into city prototypes: gives a brief overview of the cities prototypes and the solutions involved.

¹ https://zenodo.org/communities/up2030_he/

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096405/results>

- ❖ Section 4 – UP2030 solutions – Integration plan: provides an overview of the technological roadmap towards integration into cities prototypes.
- ❖ Section 5 – Conclusions and Next Steps.
- ❖ Section 6 – References.

2 UP2030 solutions – A practical guide

This section provides an overview of the diverse tools and solutions available within the UP2030 project. To ensure the effective integration of the tools into the city prototypes, a matchmaking process was conducted, more information about this process can be found on [D4.2 - UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities 2](#) (Kapetas, L. et al., 2023). This process involved assessing the tools offered by project partners and determining their suitability for addressing the specific needs and challenges of each city prototype. While some tools were immediately applicable, others required significant adaptations to align with the cities’ contexts, goals, and technological environments. Additionally, certain tools were deemed less relevant, thus, not a good fit for the prototypes at this stage of the project. In that case, the corresponding tool providers focused on other solutions more aligned with the cities vision.

2.1 Climate Proofing – Buro Happold

Climate Proofing is an assessment methodology to quickly assess urban development projects upon their impacts and potentials on both climate mitigation and adaptation and provide high-level recommendations on how to set out targets, baselines, and project-specific steps towards a climate-neutral and -resilient neighbourhood development. Climate proofing will allow quick assessments of viability (pre-feasibility) of future projects and their impacts/potentials on climate mitigation and adaptation climate-neutrality and -resilience. The tool integrates synergies between mitigation and adaptation measures, aiming that measures on mitigation don’t negatively affect adaptation and vice versa.

Methodology phases:

- In a first step, aspirations, and goals of the city are identified and translated into project and sector specific targets. Existing policies, regulations, and guidelines are reviewed.
- Second, the cities are supported in how to assess existing data, identify gaps, and potential substitutes for missing data – e.g., reference data or industry experience.
- Based on the gathered data and information, cities are guided on how carbon dioxide (CO2) emissions from different sectors are assessed (e.g., building operation, embodied carbon, mobility, carbon sinks).
- Finally, recommendations are given regarding measures and pathways to reduce carbon emissions in the respective sectors, as well as strategies for reducing the impacts of climate change (e.g., heat island effect). The proposed measures aim ideally to support each other, or at least do no significant harm in any of the considered aspects. This would then translate into recommendations to be applied through formal or informal planning instruments in the subsequent planning phases.

Table 1: Climate Proofing: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Buro Happold (BH)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Münster

2.2 Data-Driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design – TSPA

The Parametric Design and Assessment tool aims to procedurally investigate possible spatial configurations and urban design scenarios through a step-by-step parametric generation of urban environments (digital twin space), while simultaneously analysing the cross-impact of the proposed scenarios on each relevant design criteria (e.g. Walkability, Density, Solar energy).

The Parametric design approach helps cities better understand the impact of the design decisions through active involvement in the design process, and allowing for a real time analysis of the impact design choices may have on the neighbouring environment. The tool also allows designing spaces through parameter setting, which optimizes designs to meet pre-set target goals. Thus, the tool allows visualising the existing (spatial / environmental / socio-economic / geographic / urban) context in easy-to-understand fashion, to illustrate the impact of current trends on short, intermediate, and long-term scales, as well as to perform performance evaluation of selected planning and design options to achieve high level targets and goals. The methods utilise GIS and/or parametric design models to evaluate various urban development scenarios to identify dependencies and impacts of climate-positive actions and design solutions across sectors and scales.

Figure 1. Data-Driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design user interface. Source: TSPA

Table 2. Data-Driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

Provider	TSPA
Type	Software, Methodology
City Prototypes	Granollers

2.3 CLIMACT Prio tool – Global Green Growth Institute

CLIMACT Prio is a climate awareness, decision support and capacity building MS Excel tool with a few Visual Basic features for screening and prioritizing of local climate change actions.

CLIMACT Prio tool utilizes a multi-criteria approach to assist decision makers and urban planners to:

1. Identify a wide range of decision criteria and set priorities among objectives,
2. Perform an analysis and assessment of climate change (mitigation or adaptation) actions and based on the selected criteria,
3. Identify and rank the most suitable climate actions for the city climate change action plan.

The Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) functionality identifies and weights multiple criteria (environmental, economic, social, institutional, etc.) that can be used to assess the different climate mitigation and adaptation actions. The tool provides a systematic process where individuals or groups can follow a step-by-step guided weighting criteria approach to understand and determine the most important criteria and objectives that need to be considered during the assessment of the climate actions. This process facilitates stakeholders' discussion and exchange of information and knowledge.

CLIMACT Prio can be used for several purposes:

- *Screening and rapid feasibility assessment*: The tool can be used for screening and a rapid feasibility assessment process of climate actions considering different feasibility criteria.
- *Decision support and assessment of climate actions*: The final objective of the tools is to provide support for decision making and assessment of different climate actions by considering multiple criteria and objectives. As such, the tool can support the development of a city climate change action plan.
- *Prioritization process*: The tool through its specific features can facilitate the identification and setting of city's multiple objectives (environmental, economic, social, institutional, etc.) and priorities to be used for the assessment (and prioritization) of climate change actions.
- *Stakeholders' co-creation and engagement process*: The tool supports the prioritization process of climate actions by facilitation the active engagement of stakeholders in the process in different stages such as objectives setting, selection of climate actions, screening of long list of climate actions and assessment, criteria weights, and scoring/ assessment of climate actions. The tool aims to facilitate a stakeholder's co-creation and engagement process to lead to the prioritization of climate actions for the development of a city climate change action plan.
- *Knowledge generation and sharing*: Through the stakeholders' co-creation and engagement process in the different stages of the prioritization of climate actions, stakeholders can exchange and generate knowledge and information regarding the climate change challenges, mitigation, and adaptation objectives and sectoral and cross-sectoral climate actions and solutions suitable for the city.
- *Capacity building*: Because of all the above features, the CLIMACT Prio tool has been widely used for capacity building and training of city officials and urban planners on climate actions decision support and prioritization as part of city's climate action planning process.

Table 3. CLIMACT Prio tool: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI)
<i>Type</i>	Excel tool
<i>City Prototypes</i>	No city matching. GGGI is currently focusing on the development of the Green Economy Model tool.

2.4 Green Economy Model – GGGI

The Green Economy Model (GEM) solution is a simulation tool of climate interventions and low carbon development scenarios against environmental and macroeconomic indicators. It is an integrated model — which considers the interlinkages existing between populations, economic activity, and environmental outcomes — that assesses various economy-wide emission reduction pathways. Therefore, it supports the estimation of the economic outcomes of decarbonization, including the economic valuation of several social and environmental externalities, in addition to job gains and losses.

The GEM model was designed explicitly to analyse green economy and low carbon development scenarios. GEM is built using the Systems Thinking and the System Dynamics (SD) methodology, serving primarily as a knowledge integrator. SD is a form of computer simulation modelling designed to facilitate policy planning in the medium to long term across key economic sectors and subsectors (energy, industry, waste management, agriculture and Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF). The purpose of SD is not to make precise predictions of the future, or to optimize performance; rather, these models are used to inform policy formulation, forecasting policy outcomes, and leading to the creation of a resilient and well-balanced strategy.

GEM has several objectives, including:

- *Informing policy formulation and evaluation*, with a focus on shaping consumption and production towards a greener economic development paradigm.
- *Simulating impacts of green economy policies*, across sectors prioritized in national sustainable development plans, such as agriculture, forestry, fishery, energy, and mining.
- *Generating systemic, cross-sectorial scenarios* over time that address environmental, economic, and social issues in a single coherent framework, simulating the main short-, medium-, and longer-term impacts of investing in a greener economy.
- *Incorporating relationships between society, economy, and environment*. GEM provides policymakers with a tool that explicitly includes the relationships existing between society, the economy, and the environment, allowing for a better understanding of the dynamics of the system analysed and the design of better policies.

GEM includes four key capitals (physical, human, social, and natural) as interconnected via the explicit representation of feedback loops (reinforcing or balancing). Policies can be implemented to strengthen growth (i.e., reinforcing loops) or curb change (e.g., by strengthening balancing loops). In this specific study GEM is used to (1) test the effectiveness of individual policies and investments (by assessing their impact within and across sectors, and for social, economic, and environmental indicators); and (2) inform

development planning (by assessing the outcomes of the simultaneous implementation of various intervention options).

Table 4. Green Economy Model: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	GGGI
<i>Type</i>	Simulation Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	-

2.5 UDCW facilitation toolkit/P-GIS (Participatory GIS) solution – UCCRN

The Urban Design Climate Workshops (UDCW) Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools that allow to engage different typologies of city actors (experts: decision makers, city officials, planning/design practitioners; and non-experts: third sector and citizens) in a co-created climate resilient design process.

The toolkit includes:

1. Collaborative mapping through analogue (boards/stickers) or digital (online mapping) tools (with experts and non-experts);
2. Urban Climate Factors/City visions/local needs matching (Priority mapping/co-design exercise with non-experts);
3. A day in the life (Visioning exercise with experts and non-experts);
4. 3D neighbourhood configurator tool (co-design exercise with experts), linked to the 3D Modelling tool – see UDCW simulation toolkit (section 2.6) – to simplify the development of design proposals to test.

The main co-produced data include perception of climate risks, local issues and opportunities, quality of urban spaces, environmental pressures, social capital, socio-spatial issues, infrastructures and service availability, everyday risks, community, and stakeholders’ priorities.

Participatory Geographic Information System

Participatory Geographic Information System (P-GIS) is used to incorporate all the information gathered with the engagement of communities and stakeholders. The final mapping can be integrated in a GIS format and used as complementary input in the UDCW Simulation toolkit.

The UDCW P-GIS helps to create participatory maps to spatialize and visualise the local knowledge and priorities gathered within the UDCW “Collaborative mapping and co-design” phase, which is usually acquired through a combination of digital and analogue tools, in a single web-based mapping platform (such as open street map). The on-line open-source maps are intended as a platform in which both top-down (expert-driven) and bottom-up (participants) information is seamlessly and available for communities and decision-makers. The tool enables the integration of community knowledge about a neighbourhood/district and guides the contextualizing of design strategies and specific solutions in a specific territory.

UDCW experts develop maps with baseline information that can include qualitative and quantitative data (e.g., data on climate-related risks and other environmental risks, vulnerability of population, building

typologies etc.). Through a focus group or a neighbourhood walk, the engagement of participants is triggered. They are invited to develop a mapping exercise on physical maps (with stickers) to collect fine-grained bottom-up data highlighting local knowledge components, followed by a priorities’ mapping session in relation to possible transformation of the area. These data depend on the specific aim of the activity and on the specific local focus and issues to be interlinked with climate topics. UDCW experts collect the data and implement digital maps to deliver a public platform of knowledge sharing available for communities and decision makers.

UDCW facilitation toolkit goals:

- *Co-produce relevant data and knowledge about climate risks* and local issues and opportunities with local stakeholders and communities.
- *Collaboratively identify and visualize local needs and priorities*, empowering urban stakeholders and communities with respect to high-level targets and goals related to sustainable and climate-resilient development.
- *Train technical experts* on design-friendly tools enabling climate and environmental analyses at neighbourhood scale through the support of UCCRN simulation services.

The UDCW Facilitation toolkit supports the implementation of the “Collaborative mapping and co-design” phase of the UDCW Methodology (section 2.7), and it can be used as a standalone toolkit (and its tools as standalone components for partial analyses), but it provides significant additional outcomes if used in synergy with the UDCW Simulation toolkit (section 2.6). When used in synergy with the UDCW Simulation toolkit, bottom-up data can be integrated to quantitative modelling of climate change impacts (heat and flood) and the assessment of mitigation/adaptation benefits and social, economic and environmental co-benefits of climate-resilient planning/design solutions.

Table 5. UDCW facilitation toolkit/P-GIS solution: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Urban Climate Change Research Network – European Hub (UCCRN)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Thessaloniki, Rio de Janeiro

2.6 UDCW simulation toolkit – UCCRN

The UDCW simulation toolkit consists of a set of technological tools (GIS and 3D Modelling Algorithm Aided Design tools) for heat waves and flood hazard/impact modelling. The models are based on the elaboration of climate projections downscaled to include urban microclimate conditions and simulate the impacts of heat waves on population (mortality rate increase, hospitalization, including economic direct and indirect impacts) and the effect of seasonal temperature trends variation on energy demand for building heating/cooling, and impacts of floods on buildings and open spaces (direct and indirect damage to structure and content).

The tools can measure the climate benefits in terms of adaptation and mitigation measures through fully quantitative indicators, also including a quantitative/qualitative assessment of social, economic and environmental co-benefits associated to climate resilient development strategies

UDCW simulation toolkit goals:

- *Integrate urban climate design principles in city planning*, urban and building/open space design.
- *Perform science-based climate hazard/impact and mitigation/adaptation assessments based on IPCC AR6 and EU Taxonomy/ “do no significant harm” approaches.*
- *Streamlining the use of quantitative indicators* to support multi-scale evaluation of planning and design solutions (urban, neighbourhood and building scale).
- *Link climate benefits* (mitigation and adaptation) of proposed plans/projects with social, economic and environmental co-benefits of climate-resilient developments.

The UDCW simulation toolkit supports the implementation of the “Climate Analysis Mapping” and “Planning and Design” phases of the UDCW Methodology (section 2.7). It can be used as a standalone toolkit (and its tools as standalone components for partial analyses) but provides significant additional outcomes if used in synergy with the UDCW facilitator toolkit (section 2.5).

Table 6. UDCW simulation toolkit solution: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	UCCRN
<i>Type</i>	Software toolkit
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Thessaloniki, Rio de Janeiro

2.7 UDCW methodology – UCCRN

The methodology focuses on sequential and iterative phases that lead to the development of the project through a multi-disciplinary and multi-scale approach. These are implemented with the support of UCCRN-multidisciplinary experts and urban stakeholders, defining an intervention model that combines knowledge-sharing and co-design actions with urban decision makers and local communities together with the development of simulations based on computational design tools to control the main indicators that determine the performance of buildings and open spaces in relation to climatic stress conditions.

Phases:

- *Climate/microclimate analysis mapping* identifies urban areas most affected by extreme events and seasonal variations, including local climate projections, as preliminary project information.

Historical climate data and Regional Climate Models (RCMs) are processed through simulation models providing as output urban heat hotspots and flood zones; parametric 3D modelling tools assess technical solutions at the block/building scale, integrating climate-resilience aspects with other green building and environmental design criteria and benchmarks.

- *Collaborative mapping and co-design* aim at assessing the quality of urban spaces and combining climate-related considerations with needs and expectations of local communities.

Stakeholders’ engagement methods (e.g. collaborative mapping, gamification and codesign), involving residents, local administrations, neighbourhood and category associations, allow a shared reading of the main critical aspects of the urban system in relation to environmental, functional-spatial and socio-economic aspects. The synthesis of the results outlines a picture of shared needs and possible divergence elements between categories of stakeholders to integrate in the project.

- *Planning and design* are based on a critical review of the information collected to identify synergies and trade-offs that can be implemented in relation to the planning initiatives envisaged by the local authorities.

Urban plans and building regulations define the limits within which to develop the most appropriate technical-design strategies and solutions to achieve the set of objectives. Visual tools will link the multiple factors orienting local policy and transformative actions and possible meta design layouts to support the production of innovative solutions addressing climate change impacts while increasing environmental quality in cities.

- *Post-intervention evaluation* is intended as a sequence of activities to evaluate the benefits of the proposed solutions in terms of microclimate, energy and environmental performance, as well as compliance with community priorities. The tools include instruments for simulation-driven/indicator-based scenario comparisons, and for gathering direct feedback from residents and local stakeholders.

The UDCW methodology is supported by the UDCW Simulation toolkit (section 2.6 and the UDCW Facilitation toolkit (section 2.5).

Table 7. UDCW methodology: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	UCCRN
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Thessaloniki, Rio de Janeiro

2.8 Resilience Assessment Framework – LNEC/AQUATEC

The Resilience Assessment Framework (RAF) is a solution resulting from the H2020 RESCCUE³ project that helps decision makers to select the most efficient measures, in terms of both their costs and the degree of risk reduction, to optimally increase cities’ resilience to climate change.

As data is scarce in some situations, the methodology behind this platform is flexible and two assessments can be conducted: preliminary and detailed. The first will provide a rank of climate adaptation measures for a specific strategy. In case enough information is available, a detailed assessment may follow a process to analyse the effectiveness of adaptation scenarios (i.e., a set of measures acting jointly) according to user-defined prioritization criteria. Graphs are provided at the end of the process to summarize the results.

³ <https://toolkit.resccue.eu/>

Figure 2. Resilience Assessment Framework web platform. Source LNEC.

Table 8. Resilience Assessment Framework: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC), AQUATEC
<i>Type</i>	Web platform
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Granollers

2.9 Liveable Cities Index methodology – CETAQUA

The Liveable Cities Index methodology is designed to determine the overall or sectoral health situation of cities (environmental, economic, social) through the integration of a variety of variables and measurement parameters gathered from public data. The multi-method tool uses 75 indicators distributed in five categories: Society, Environmental Quality, Health, Land Use, and Resources. Through the collection of public municipal data, the Liveable Cities Index methodology provides either an overall or sectoral picture of the cities’ health situation, giving direct results that allow the identification of improvement points. The comparability element of the tool provides a global picture, where each city can learn by comparing the assessment with other cities.

The result is an aggregated index of liveability and a liveability ranking which provides cities with a decision-making tool to identify their weaknesses and options/solutions for improvement related to society, environmental quality, health, land use, and resources.

Table 9. Liveable Cities Index methodology: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	CETAQUA
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	-

2.10 Water-smartness Assessment Framework | Tool for circularity in the urban water cycle – LNEC

The Water-smartness Assessment Framework Tool is an objective-driven comprehensive framework and tool (web-based dashboard) that was developed to support multi-stakeholder and strategic decision-making towards the transition to a water-smart society developed under H2020 B-Water Smart project⁴.

The tool is an assessment tool itself with a consistent portfolio of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for supporting the development and the monitoring of a strategic plan for water-smartness, addressing technical, economic (circular economy), societal (governance, policy, acceptability), environmental, and risk dimensions.

The tool allows measuring the performance towards five strategic objectives “Ensuring water for all relevant uses”, “Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society”, “Boosting value creation around water”, “Promoting adaptive change towards resilient infrastructure”, and “Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation”, aligned with 15 assessment criteria and materialised in 60 indicators/indices⁵.

Table 10. Water-smartness Assessment Framework | Tool for circularity in the urban water cycle: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	LNEC
<i>Type</i>	Web-based dashboard
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Lisbon

2.11 Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle – LNEC

Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle is a guide on good practice in evaluating measurement and uncertainty resulted from the EMUE project⁶. This guide supports the assessment of uncertainty and reliability of the quantitative measurements of environmental variables (e.g., precipitation).

The methods can be used by cities to assess and quantitatively measure the quality of data relevant to climate adaptation and sustainable development of urban environments, informing progress assessments

⁴ <https://b-watersmart.eu/>

⁵ <https://b-watersmart.eu/results-downloads/water-smartness-assessment-framework/>

⁶ <http://empir.npl.co.uk/emue/>

of implemented solutions, by providing computational procedures allowing estimating measurements uncertainties of models’ parameters and measured quantities.

The main objective is to improve the confidence of quantitative measurements of variables relevant to climate adaptation and sustainable urban environment by evaluating measurement uncertainties thus supporting improved data analysis and knowledge-based decision-making.

Table 11. Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	LNEC
<i>Type</i>	Software toolkit
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Lisbon

2.12 Climate Resilient City Tool – Deltares

The Climate Resilient City Tool (CRCTool) aims to support collaborative climate adaptation planning and to promote multi-disciplinary dialogue on adaptation options to increase urban climate resilience. The tool contains a database of over 50 adaptation measures including descriptions, pictures of best practices and references for further reading.

The CRCTool is easy to use by both experts and non-experts in the field of urban planning and adaptation and can be used in a workshop setting with multiple stakeholders as well as behind a desk.

The CRCTool is developed around a central interactive map window that displays base layers like a map and/or aerial photograph that is used as spatial reference. On top of these base layers’ semi-transparent thematic maps can be displayed like an elevation map, flood, or heat stress maps that help to understand the climate challenges in an area and to choose effective locations for interventions.

Adaptation measures can be drawn on the map as polygon, line, or point element and the measure appears in the list of applied measures. Next, the main properties of the measure, like water storage depth and contributing area can be given, after which climate resilience and cost KPIs are calculated and shown in the user interface. The main KPIs are: storage volume, return time factor, additional groundwater recharge, additional evapotranspiration, heat reduction, cool areas, construction costs and maintenance costs. The hydrological KPIs are based on a multi reservoir model: the effect on heat stress is based on statistical relations and the cost figures are based on unit costs.

Tools functionalities allow the users to locate the measures on a map and explore and compare adaptation options for a project area. It provides information on the effectiveness of measures to reduce stormwater flooding, urban heat stress and drought. Additional information on construction and maintenance costs is also available. The CRCTool encourages the use of Nature-Based Solutions; traditional grey measures are included to enable comparison.

Table 12. CRCTool: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Deltares
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	No city matching.

	Deltares is focusing on the Hydroflows solution for Rio de Janeiro
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2.13 Draxis UP2030 Decision Support System – DRAXIS

Draxis UP2030 Decision support system (DDSS) for smart cities is a state-of-the-art geospatial intelligence platform with clear vision of providing innovative tools and services to citizen and organizations.

The solution can combine data from multiple sources (Internet of Things (IoT), geospatial, satellite, open source and citizen data) of any format or data following common measurement standards.

The DDSS aims to facilitate the integration of other tools to the utilization platform by offering a complete solution for the collection, processing, and analysis of data via geospatial intelligence and machine learning algorithms in order to produce new information and services that will elevate the municipality, the people and their potential.

Table 13. Draxis UP2030 Decision Support System: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	DRAXIS
<i>Type</i>	Web software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Thessaloniki

2.14 Air Quality Monitoring and Forecasting Service – LINKS

Air Quality Monitoring and Forecasting Service is monitoring and forecasting of air pollutant levels in urban area by exploiting both satellite, meteorological and traffic data. Its main objectives are to provide accurate and up-to date information on air quality in the interested area to public health officials, residents, and other stakeholders and to also identify patterns in pollutants level, including impacts of factors such as weather, traffic and human activity.

Table 14. Air quality monitoring and forecasting service: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Fondazione LINKS (LINKS)
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Lisbon

2.15 Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs – LINKS

The Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST) (formerly Ecosystem Services Assessment) is a tool used to identify, quantify, and evaluate a wide range of benefits provided by the natural environment, supporting stakeholders in policy development and decision-making.

InVEST works on ecosystem services, defined as the goods and services provided by habitats to humans. These are divided into:

1. Provisioning (e.g., raw material production)

2. Regulating services (e.g., air purification)
3. Supporting (e.g. habitat provision)
4. Cultural (e.g. ecotourism, health)

The outcome is a map that illustrates the value (including economic) of ecosystem services provided by each geographic unit, while also assessing the current state, trends, and conditions of ecosystems and their services in urban areas.

Figure 3. InVEST solution high level interface. Source: LINKS

Table 15. Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs - InVEST: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	LINKS
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Milan

2.16 Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis – LINKS

Urban Heat Island (UHI) Risk Analysis is a methodology based on satellite data analysis for extreme temperature events, such as heat waves or the occurrence of UHI phenomena. Heat waves and urbanization intensify the UHI effect, defined as the temperature difference between urban and rural areas caused by the excess heat emitted and the solar gains trapped by the urbanized environment.

The tool is able to identify the highly heat-exposed urban areas to intervene in advance for ensuring the functionality of already existing technological infrastructures (hard and soft).

Table 16. Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	LINKS
<i>Type</i>	Software

City Prototypes	No city matching. LINKS is focusing on InVEST and Air quality monitoring and forecasting service
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2.17 Urban Building/Transport Energy Model – METU

UBTEM stands for Urban Building/Transport Energy Model and is a computational tool used to simulate and analyse the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions of buildings and transportation systems in urban areas. It incorporates advanced computational methods such as digital energy twin and artificial intelligence for building energy retrofit, photovoltaic (PV) integration in the built environment and electric micro-mobility in order to initiate positive energy neighbourhoods. The tool helps decision-makers to understand the potential impacts of different policy interventions and technology solutions on energy consumption, emissions, and social benefits such as reducing energy poverty and overheating-related health risks.

The solution provides an Urban-scale modelling, simulation and machine learning based calculation that enables:

- The analysis of building energy performance and occupant comfort.
- The evaluation of the retrofit scenarios on building energy performance and occupant comfort.
- The analysis of the impact of climate change on building energy performance.
- The potential PV-based electricity generation estimation.
- The analysis of return of investments of installed PV and battery technologies.
- Find optimal locations for PV-integrated charging stations for micro-mobility (i.e. e-scooters)

Figure 4. UBEM of the Istanbul Kadikoy neighbourhood. Source: METU

Figure 5. Roof modelling for PV analysis in Istanbul Kadikoy. Source: METU

UBTEM is integrated in the Integrated Digital Twin (DT) Framework (section 2.21) developed in task 3.2 (T3.2) – “Digital Twins of urban environments for energy integration and GHG emissions reduction”.

Table 17. Urban Building/Transport Energy Model: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Middle East Technical University (METU)/ODTU GUNAM
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Istanbul

2.18 Building Information Model (BIM) module & Building Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) module – CIRCE

The aim of this solution is to assess the impact of various rehabilitation scenarios and other city-level measures to recommend those most suitable for minimizing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This tool facilitates the current assessment for the optimization of the building envelope in terms of thermal transmittance and evaluates its impact and that of residential energy systems by exploiting detailed modelling and environmental impact analysis. It plays a crucial role for city councils and municipalities in monitoring and managing CO2 emissions and energy consumption across different districts, encompassing buildings and the renovation of building energy systems. By optimising building designs to improve thermal transmittance, the tool helps to reduce the energy required for heating and cooling, which is a significant component of a building’s total energy consumption. By providing detailed projections for future scenarios in 2030 and 2050, the tool aids in the strategic planning and implementation of sustainable interventions. This enables local governments to make informed decisions that align with their long-term environmental targets and sustainability goals, ensuring effective adaptation to climate change and progress toward net zero objectives.

BIM module & Building LCA module is in the Integrated DT Framework (section 2.21) developed in T3.2.

Table 18. BIM module & Building LCA assessment module: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Fundación Circe Centro De Investigación De Recursos Y Consumos Energéticos (CIRCE)
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Istanbul

2.19 MIRA solution for Cities as Digital Twins – Gruppo Maggioli

MIRA as a DT platform provides cities with the ability to create virtual replicas of urban environments, by integrating real-time information from sensors or any other available source of data. These replicas allow city planners and officials to simulate various scenarios, optimize infrastructure, and enhance decision-making processes. A City DT can be considered as a network of interconnected DTs, each one representing different assets (e.g. buildings, parking slots) or networks (e.g. neighbourhoods, public spaces, etc.).

For the purposes of UP2030, this tool goes beyond assessing the impact of building materials by integrating energy storage, energy systems renovation, PV installation, and mobility integration into its simulations. It allows users to visualize pilot locations and predict future energy demands for both 2030 and 2050 under optimal scenarios. Users can observe the potential energy savings and reductions in greenhouse gas

emissions through intuitive graphs and charts. MIRA acts also as a point of entry for users, an input for ingesting data and a visualization platform for data and analytics produced by other tools in the bundle.

Figure 6. MIRA city digital twin map view. Source: MAG

Figure 7. MIRA user interface. Source: MAG

MIRA is integrated in the Integrated DT Framework (section 2.21) developed in T3.2.

Table 19. MIRA solution for Cities as Digital Twins: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Gruppo Maggioli (MAG)
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Istanbul

2.20 Circular Urban Planning – ETH

Circular Urban Planning tool aims to support decision-making process towards improving circularity in built environment through implementation of reuse strategies at urban scales. The objective of the tool is to assess the time when and spatialise on a map where reusable elements can potentially be reclaimed. Reusable elements will be catalogued in a database together with the associated circularity metrics and life cycle environmental performance. The ultimate objective is to increase the reusing rate and flow of materials from disassembly and demolition sites, ultimately extending the end-of-life of buildings to reduce the production of raw materials.

Circular Urban Planning is a modelling framework with a bottom-up approach, that integrates material and flows analysis (MFA) over time, into the new parametric model that combines dynamic life cycle assessment (DLCA) and circularity assessment (CA). To apply these methods on a pilot city neighbourhood, and perform analyses that yield robust and reliable results, it is critical to rely on national and contextual databases, such as cadastral data, geographic information systems, environmental flow coefficients in construction materials, material composition of typical building types, etc.

Circular Urban Planning module is in the Integrated DT Framework (section 2.21) produced in T3.2.

Table 20. Circular Urban Planning: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	ETH (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich)
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Not part of a city prototype.

2.21 Integrated Digital Twin Framework

In T3.2, an integration framework was proposed to extract the functionalities of the DT solutions provided in this task, with the goal of adding value for stakeholders involved in decision-making and in designing decarbonization, energy, and climate plans. The Integrated DT Framework includes four digital tools, each intended for different purposes:

- BIM Module and LCA: Integration of construction features for the creation of standard energy consumption profiles and the design of rehabilitation plans. (section 2.18)
- UBTEM: Integration of energy models with renewable resources and mobility in urban environments. (section 2.17)
- MIRA Digital Platform: Platform for visualising results and potential real-time monitoring. (section 2.19)

- Circular Urban Planning: Development of circularity strategies through energy rehabilitation of buildings. (section 2.20)

For more information, please refer [to D3.4 – “Bundle of Digital Twin tools for net zero decision making 1”](#)(Castan, M.A. et al., 2024).

Table 21. Integrated Digital Twin Framework: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	CIRCE, METU/ODTU GUNAM, MAG, ETH
<i>Type</i>	Software
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Istanbul

2.22 Modular Urban Farm – VM

The Modular Urban Farm is a Bio – Socio – Technical modular educational urban farming IoT solution that leverages the "Universal Data Machine," a framework centred around integrating data for machine learning and data analysis.

The Modular Urban features:

- Vertical farming modules designed for efficient space utilization in urban environments.
- Integrated hydroponic or other systems for soil-less cultivation of crops.
- LED lighting systems to provide optimal light spectrum and intensity for plant growth.
- Automated climate control systems to regulate temperature, humidity, and CO2 levels, plant health, nutrient levels, and environmental conditions.
- Water management systems for efficient usage and recycling of water resources.
- Educational program (Green Polytechnic – 20 modules developed) to teach citizens about sustainable agriculture and urban food systems.
- Demonstration areas showcasing different cultivation techniques and plant varieties and looking classes and recipe demonstrations showcasing delicious and nutritious plant-based meals.
- Interactive displays and information boards explaining the impact of urban food systems on climate change.
- Integration with renewable energy sources to reduce carbon footprint.
- Implementation of circular economy principles, such as composting organic waste and utilizing it as fertilizer.
- Online platforms or mobile applications to connect citizens, share knowledge, and track their farming progress (through external digital platform integration).
- Integration with smart city infrastructure for data sharing and analysis to optimize resource usage and environmental impact.

Table 22. Modular Urban Farm: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Vesela Motika (VM)
<i>Type</i>	Physical Prototype
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Zagreb

2.23 GeoKey/Community Maps – MfC

Community Maps is a mobile-friendly web application which facilitates participatory mapping through community engagement to support urban design and planning. It allows stakeholders to create digital representations of physical spaces, integrating community perceptions, aspirations, and planned interventions. The tool facilitates democratic, participatory urban planning by combining data on current conditions (like infrastructure and environmental quality), design scenarios, with stakeholder input and planned urban interventions.

Community Maps supports the reduction in silo working by providing a visual way to share information, identify existing and planned programs, which may have potential overlaps or synergies, alongside pinpointing gaps for intervention.

This online mapping platform can:

- Bring together different groups and departments for a specific aim.
- Visualise and share complex information.
- Elicit local knowledge.
- Allow transparent communications.
- Inspire collective action at a local and global level.

User generated content and relevant information can be visualised, shared on a map and discussed within and across communities. The platform has been used for numerous research projects in various contexts, locations and languages.

Table 23. GeoKey/Community Maps: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Mapping for Change (MfC)
<i>Type</i>	Software, web platform
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Belfast, Budapest

2.24 Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping – UCAM

Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping is a methodology being developed within UP2030 to help city authorities manage carbon emissions more effectively. The framework maps depict how carbon emission data flows within city governance to assess the maturity of data collection and usage. This helps cities

improve data governance, especially by enhancing information flow across different sectors and departments. The aim is to support better decision-making for carbon neutrality and net zero goals.

City managers need visibility into how carbon data is used across the organization to make informed decisions and investments in carbon management. Better processes are needed to improve the trust, transparency, and accessibility of carbon data among teams and stakeholders.

By interviewing stakeholders, this methodology maps the use and flow of carbon data across the organization, addressing data quality issues. The goal is to provide cities with a strategic baseline for managing carbon by understanding (1) what data they hold, (2) how it is used, and (3) how interventions can improve their capacity to manage carbon effectively.

Figure 8. Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping flow diagram. Source: UCAM

Table 24. Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	University of Cambridge (UCAM)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Belfast, Münster, Zagreb

2.25 Learning and Action Alliances method – ICA

The Learning and Action Alliances (LAA) method is a collaborative approach/solution used to address complex social, environmental, or organizational challenges (multifaceted issues) for meaningful solutions.

LAA involves bringing together diverse stakeholders with different perspectives, knowledge, and expertise to collectively learn, problem-solve, and take action to create positive change. LAA aims to foster sustainable solutions to complex challenges by leveraging the collective wisdom and resources of diverse stakeholders.

The LAA method can be used for various types of analysis or tasks of multifaceted issues. It can be applied in a wide range of fields, such as community development, environmental conservation, social justice, public policy, and organizational change, among others.

Table 25. Learning and Action Alliances method: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	ICA (I-CATALIST)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	No direct matching but LAAs were established in all cities to support the participatory principles of UP2030.

2.26 Trainings for Capacity Building – ISOCARP

Trainings for capacity-building are tailored to specific locales, addressing organizational gaps in knowledge and skills related to urban planning and sustainability. The trainings enable the participants, specifically the leadership and employees of urban municipalities, to carry out future-proof sustainable urban planning in their respective cities. The comprehensive capacity-building program emphasizes two-way, peer-to-peer learning and a combination of theory (i.e. interactive lectures) and practice (i.e. workshops and exercises). The trainings are tailored to specific contexts and draw on local knowledge to increase urban planning capacities in meaningful and effective manners. The trainings are led by experts in the field based on their knowledge of specific subjects and geographical areas.

Table 26. Trainings for Capacity Building: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	ISOCARP Institute- Centre for Urban Excellence (ISOCARP)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Rotterdam (to be confirmed)

2.27 Storytelling for Participatory Exchange - ISOCARP

The Storytelling methodology provides a basis for developing spaces that facilitate the co-exchange of knowledge, ideas, experiences and obstacles between varying stakeholders. The premise is based around the idea that through telling stories, individuals can separate themselves from their cognitive perspective and adapt an affective mode of communicating. This allows for exchanges to bypass potential conflicts, leading to productive and intersectional points of co-learning. Storytelling for participatory exchange is an applicable solution to multiple contexts. The process involves capacity building activities in which the process of constructing and delivering storytelling workshops/events is facilitated. Through this solution, governors will gain an understanding of how to draw multiple stakeholders into conversations and how to use storytelling as a method for co-creative decision-making. The solution focuses on the equal levelling of voices and construction of neutral spaces to share ideas and perspectives.

Table 27. Storytelling for Participatory Exchange: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	ISOCARP
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Budapest

2.28 Neutrality Story Maps – VUB/CERTH

Neutrality Story Maps (NSMs) is a mobile-friendly web platform that serves as a digital tool that:

1. allows cities to raise awareness about climate change by communicating climate-related challenges and initiatives they have put in place to tackle them and,
2. empowers citizens to express their interests and hopes for their future in their city, stemming from their local lived experience with climate change.

The tool is a type of digital storytelling that helps reveal the thoughts, sensations, concerns, issues, and hopes of residents in the UP2030 cities, especially vulnerable groups, through a narrative multimedia format. Starting from the idea that everyone is inherently creative, storyteller-citizens and policymakers are provided tools, templates, tips and tricks – but above all; freedom – to shape their climate stories on the NSM platform in a way that is completely their own and reflects their living world and personal experiences.

The web application (aka NSM Platform) allows cities and citizens to register, create stories, and view them on a timeline and a map. Stories are posts made up of multiple pages, each featuring different formats like images, video, audio, text, or a combination of these. They can also be displayed in full screen using the “scrollytelling” technique. Cities can create threads (groups of stories on specific topics) and resources (articles, educational materials, etc.). Users can interact by liking or commenting on stories, and the platform offers cities analytics and customizable settings.

Table 28. Neutrality Story Maps: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Centre for Research & Technology, Hellas (CERTH)
<i>Type</i>	Web tool
<i>City Prototypes</i>	No direct matching, but NSM is involved in all cities as an engagement tool.

Figure 9. Thessaloniki UP2030 pilot Neutrality Story Maps. Source: VUB/CERTH

2.29 Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design Method – DC

The Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design Method (CYFUD) is a tool to design small-scale interventions in city’s public space, aiming to enhance the public realm’s spatial quality, particularly for children and young people.

Objectives:

- Create public spaces that reflect the needs and aspirations of children and young people growing up in cities.
- Include children and youth in the city’s planning processes and establish a communication channel between young people and decision-makers to enable bottom-up initiatives and action.
- Empower children and young people to take climate action and shape their future.

CYFUD aligns with a broader perspective of more resilient and sustainable cities that create safe and friendly environments for the younger citizens to grow up and thrive. For this purpose, CYFUD is a tailored application of existing validated guidelines and frameworks for public participation. In doing so, the younger citizens are empowered to take an equal role in the public discourse.

Table 29. Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design Method: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Design Clips (DC)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Belfast

2.30 Transformative governance instruments – ADELPHI

The tool will highlight replicable governance instruments that support cities’ transformation to reach their climate neutrality, social justice and resilience goals. It will focus on hard and soft policies, but also other governance aspects that allow sector-wide and multi-actor mainstreaming as well as upscaling of first initiatives, among other transformation processes.

Table 30. Transformative governance instruments: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	ADELPHI
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	-

2.31 City Resilience Framework & Index – RCities

The aim of the City Resilience Framework (CRF) is to promote systems-thinking in cities. The CRF has been applied in over 100 cities worldwide who contextualize it to strengthen their resilience, i.e. their capacity to respond to acute shocks and chronic pressures. The CRF is a conceptual framework, offering a common reference point for understanding what we mean when we talk about cities’ resilience. It offers an evidence-based, holistic articulation of city resilience by identifying 12 goals or outcomes contributing to resilience and structured across four dimensions:

- **People:** The health and well-being of everyone living and working in the city.
- **Organization:** The systems within the economy and society that enable urban populations to live peacefully, and act collectively.
- **Place:** The quality of infrastructure and ecosystems that protect, provide and connect us.
- **Knowledge:** Appropriate leadership and strategy enabling the city to learn from the past and take timely action.

City Resilience Index provides a comprehensive and technically robust basis for measuring city resilience that is globally applicable. It comprises 52 resilience indicators which are assessed through 156 questions, drawing upon both qualitative and quantitative data. Responses to these questions are aggregated and presented according to the 12 goals of the Framework.

Table 31. CRF & Index: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

<i>Provider</i>	Resilient Cities Network (RCities)
<i>Type</i>	Methodology
<i>City Prototypes</i>	Milan

2.32 Spatial Justice Package – TUD

The Spatial Justice Package includes six products:

1. *Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCM)*: The SJCM conceptualizes Spatial Justice by defining applicable components and goals for each justice dimension (Recognition, Procedural, and Distributive). It allows for a structured and comprehensive way of assessing how aspects of spatial justice are considered in planning and design while drawing attention to the underlying components that build each dimension.
2. *Spatial Justice Rubric (SJR)*: A set of qualitative benchmarks to promote the consistent application of justice values and just standards in urban planning and in broader aspects of governance (policy, programs, projects, reports, etc. It can be used as a playbook or for self-assessment tool, containing guidelines and recommendations for practice or public policy.
3. *Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT)*: SJBT is a qualitative evaluation tool designed to measure the application of justice considerations in urban governance and planning of a city or region.
4. *Justice Readiness Level (JRL)*: JRL is a complementary visual tool to monitor, visualize, and compare how justice is considered in decision-making. It aims to provide a shared understanding of justice considerations across many aspects of urban planning and design.
5. *Spatial Justice Handbook (SJH)*: SJH is designed for urban planners, policymakers, activists, community leaders, academics, and students interested in integrating principles of justice into spatial planning and urban development. It is a comprehensive guide for those seeking to understand and apply spatial justice concepts to create equitable and inclusive urban spaces. It also describes tools, methods, strategies, and insights to address distributive, procedural and recognition justice in spatial planning
6. *Citizen Voice (CV)*: CV is a spatial survey tool that collects qualitative information about the living environment of citizens and other local urban actors. It is a web-based, open-source software platform that works like conventional questionnaires but connected to maps. The objective is to support cities in understanding the spatial needs and aspirations of their citizenry.

More information on Spatial Justice Package can be found in [D3.8 - Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 1](#) (Rocco, R. et al. 2024).

Figure 10. Citizen Voice user interface. Source: TUD

Table 32. Spatial Justice Package: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

Provider	Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD)
Type	pdf, Excel tool, digital tool
City Prototypes	N/A

2.33 Hydroflows – Deltares

HydroFlows is a tool to rapidly assess flood risk to identify urban areas with greatest climate vulnerabilities followed by exploring design of adaptation options with nature-based solutions.

The tool consists of two components: (1) a library with building blocks required for building flood risk workflows, and (2) a framework to easily generate workflows from these building blocks that can be executed in different workflow engines.

Hydroflows aims to:

- To automate and standardize workflow setups for flood risk assessments with global data.

- Act as a starting point for local data driven assessments and “democratize’ flood risk assessment by moving knowledge and expertise to local professionals.

Figure 11. Hydroflows urban area assessment and visualization. Source: DELTARES

Table 33. Hydroflows: service provider, service type and Prototype mapping

Provider	DELTARES
Type	Software
City Prototypes	Rio de Janeiro

3 UP2030 solutions – Implementation into city prototypes

This section provides a brief overview of the cities' pilot prototype, including their vision and the services engaged in each prototype. According to Milestone 13 (Mil. 13), every city must have at least one functioning prototype by M26 (February 2025).

More information about the cities' vision and the vision co-design methodology can be found in [D2.4 – “An interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality”](#) (Covernton, E. et al., 2023) and [D2.5 – “Report on vision co-design methodology report and its application for pilot shared visions”](#) (Matulevičiūtė, A. et al. 2024). A final version of the Prototypes, along with a more detailed account of their implementation, will be presented in the third version of the roadmap report (D3.3).

It is important to note here that different approaches were taken when introducing the tools described in the previous section. In some instances, tools were actively adapted to align with the unique needs and objectives of a particular city. Meanwhile, other tools—such as the NSM, the Spatial Justice Package, and the LAAs—were designed to support all cities more generally, and so were not directly incorporated as a city-specific prototype.

3.1 Belfast Prototype

Vision:

Belfast's vision under UP2030 is to develop a framework that sets up a pathway to be *net zero at the neighbourhood level*, inspiring and guiding communities, businesses and policy makers on how to best achieve this. The framework will be tested in the pilot area of Linen Quarter district, which has been identified to become the first sustainable and net zero business district in Northern Ireland.

Prototype:

Net zero neighbourhood framework that is shaped around three thematic areas: active travel, greening, and retrofit.

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Community Maps (MfC)*
- *Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping (UCAM)*: for quantifying achieving a net zero carbon/cost
- *Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design (DC)*: as an engagement tool for children

Figure 12. Belfast Prototype comic visualization. Source: UP2030 Project

3.2 Budapest Prototype

Vision:

Together for a healthy Budapest

Creating sustainable, human-centred, and healthy urban spaces that serve the active local community. Transforming public spaces with the involvement of the community/residents. Healthy streets approach forming a liveable urban vein that serves the needs of a sustainable society

Prototype:

Knowledge Centre to bring together a coalition of experts for healthy, climate-neutral, resilient, and just urban spaces in the city.

The Knowledge Center is a collaborative platform aimed at supporting urban planners, decision-makers, and communities in creating sustainable, healthy, climate-resilient urban spaces through knowledge sharing, capacity building, and the promotion of best practices and methodologies

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design (DC)*: as an engagement tool for children
- *Community Maps (MfC)*
- *Storytelling for Participatory Exchange (ISOCARP)*

3.3 Granollers Prototype

Vision:

Become a model of urban innovation and social equity, where sustainability, inclusivity and resilience converge, with integrated green spaces, advanced mobility, and digital infrastructures to foster environmentally friendly and connected communities.

Prototype:

Planning guidelines for a climate neutral, resilient and inclusive city: a set of technical prescriptions for the development of future areas as La Bòbila neighbourhood. This integrates a draft definition of the spatial model and the results from tools implementation, that justifies the selection of resilience and climate cross cutting criteria and also the spatial model definition.

The guidelines will integrate scenarios and solutions selected by implementing RESCCUE and Parametric Design tools to fulfil the needs of the city to face main climate vulnerabilities (floods, intense temperatures and increasing social inequalities).

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Data-Driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design (TSPA)*: To provide urban design scenarios and their assessment based on spatial and environmental performance.
- *RAF*: to support decision making on selecting the optimal strategy to achieve a climate resilient neighbourhood.

3.4 Istanbul Prototype

Vision:

Forging a greener Kadikoy

Prioritising regional renewable energy production to generate impact on achieving carbon neutrality in Kadikoy. The broader aim is to create a pilot for positive-energy districts.

The pilot's objective is to identify the potential of solar panels on buildings and produce groundbreaking scientific outputs aimed at integrating this into urban transportation, presenting these outputs first to decision-makers and then to the public.

Prototype:

Decision making platform through a mix of data modelling and *on-ground implementation of urban furniture* and PV Panels in the selected neighbourhood.

Integrated Tools/Services:

- Integrated DT
 - *Urban Building Transport Energy Model (METU and GUNAM)*
 - *BIM module & Building LCA (CIRCE)*

- *MIRA solution for Cities as Digital Twins (MAG)*
- *PV integrated urban furniture*

3.5 Lisbon Prototype

Vision:

Focusing on pilot interventions at four locations – a library, a rugby club, a market, and a campus – the neighbourhood aims to implement solutions such as intelligent monitoring and decision systems, retrofitting, and the development of a catalogue of nature-based solutions to drive down carbon emissions through an inclusive and community-driven approach.

Prototype:

Develop a *concept of carbon neutral neighbourhoods*, using a multi-criterion, multidisciplinary analysis with the involvement of the municipality and the local community. Backed through data collection and technical feasibility studies.

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Air Quality Monitoring (LINKS)*
- *Water-smartness Assessment Framework | Tool for circularity in the urban water cycle*
- *Resilience Assessment Framework (LNEC)*
- *Circular Urban Planning (ETH)*

3.6 Milan Prototype

Vision:

Create districts where urban green spaces are designed to maximize their environmental, economic and social benefits, serving as resilient buffers against the impacts of climate change, in order to turn challenges into opportunities for a more liveable and fairer city for all.

Prototype:

Methodologies for the evaluation of co-benefits and resilience of climate adaptation measures in regeneration areas.

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *InVEST (LINKS)*: Maps with biophysical and economic values of the ecosystem services, report, handbook with guidelines
- *CRF (RCities)*

3.7 Münster Prototype

Vision:

Creation of a roadmap (based on the pilot project in Frauenstraße) *to guide the city administration in developing climate-friendly neighbourhoods*, supported by stakeholder participation.

Implementation of the KlimaTraining concept in neighbourhoods, focused on climate protection and adaptation measures in semi-public spaces.

Prototype:

Creation of a roadmap for climate friendly neighbourhoods to guide the city administration

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Climate proofing (BH)*
- *Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping (UCAM)*
- *NSM (VUB and CERTH)*

3.8 Rotterdam Prototype

Vision:

Upscale and leverage the lessons learnt from the Resilient BoTu 2028 program to achieve broader city goals on climate neutrality, energy transition, resilience and just transition.

Crucial that the learning resource is robust, accessible and allows for practitioners from diverse backgrounds to contextualize and replicate it in their own work.

Prototype:

Resilient District Learning Toolkit containing different learning instruments, resources and tools available within the municipal ecosystem and with LAA stakeholders for development that will be useful for other districts to use, based on their specific context

Integrated Tools/Services:

Rotterdam is looking at the possible integration of

- *Climate proofing (BH)*
- *Storytelling for Participatory Exchange (ISOCARP)*

3.9 Thessaloniki Prototype

Vision:

Creating a sustainable, thriving & climate-resilient neighbourhood of Dioikitiro that encompasses a diverse mix of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces. A healthy, green, friendly, safe, affordable & accessible neighbourhood that breaths, walks, plays, works, and offers to its residents and visitors.

Prototype:

District Climate Action Plan (DCAP) for the pilot neighbourhood, capturing status quo, needs, challenges, opportunities and vision. Supported by data modelling and technical studies.

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *UDCW methodology (UCCRN)* (including UDCW Facilitation Toolkit and UDCW Simulation Toolkit)
- *DDSS (DRAXIS)*
- *GEM (GGGI)*

3.10 Zagreb Prototype

Vision:

Develop a *low-carbon local urban food system to reduce the impact of climate change and increase resilience*.

Redefine urban agriculture by creating and closing the circular loop from school farming – food production, food consumption – food waste – composting.

Prototype:

Physical Prototypes: Green Wall, Green Room, Urban Forest in school and Urban Farm Pavillion in the zoo.

Behaviour change guide/ school curriculum update for urban farming in Zagreb

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Modular Urban Farm (VM)*
- *Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping (UCAM)*

3.11 Rio de Janeiro Prototype

Vision:

Co-create meaningful outputs that can significantly contribute to supporting urban decision-makers and practitioners in shaping just climate-resilient urban futures.

Prototype:

Development of technical studies and scenario-making related to heat and flood challenges

Integrated Tools/Services:

- *Hydroflows (Deltares)*
- *UDCW methodology (UCCRN)*

4 UP2030 solutions – Integration plan

The Transformative Pathways Roadmap emphasizes several key aspects:

- Assisting in matching the supply of solutions (tools, services, methodologies) with the demand for solutions (cities and liaisons).
- Facilitating the operationalization and integration of these solutions into the urban planning phase.
- Adapting solutions to local contextual requirements to effectively promote the climate neutrality targets of the cities.
- Driving the digital transition towards climate neutrality.

To achieve these objectives, the integration plan:

- Assists in the continuous efforts of matchmaking between cities and services by providing an overview of the offered solutions (see section 2) and their current state.
- Coordinates the co-development of tools and services and their adaptation to cities' needs by actively participating in city action workshops.
- Monitors and ensures that the offered tools and services reach the appropriate technology readiness level (TRL) by overseeing their technical implementation.
- Ensures software interoperability so that technical solutions can co-operate, allowing information and data to flow seamlessly between different solutions by collecting technical details and data inputs/outputs. Extensive information on software components and technical specifications is available in D3.1.

At this stage of the project, the majority of tools are aligned with the cities' visions, either directly or indirectly, with current efforts centred on integrating these tools into city prototypes. The technical solutions are advancing towards the appropriate TRLs, at least TRL 5 (component and/or breadboard validated in a relevant environment) (see section 4.1 and Table 34). Finally, software interoperability is progressing; DDSS (section 2.13) is the primary tool in this direction and set to be tested in a city prototype. Additional initiatives, such as the Integrated DT Framework developed in T3.2 (section 2.21), are underway to provide integrated solutions, interoperability and integration efforts which will be completed by the final city prototypes in M32 (September 2025).

4.1 TRL status

Table 35. Services TRL status

Tool	TRL		
	Start	Current	End
1 Climate proofing	6	6	8
2 City Scan - Data driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design	3	4	6
3 CLIMACT Prio tool	4	5	5
4 Green Economy Model	9	9	9
6 UDCW facilitation toolkit/P-GIS (Participatory GIS)	5	5	6
7 UDCW simulation toolkit	5	6	7
8 Resilience Assessment Framework	8	9	9
9 Liveable Cities Index methodology	8	8	8
10 Water-smartness Assessment Framework Tool for circularity in the urban water cycle	4	5	5
11 Tools for measurements in the urban water cycle	6	6	6
12 Climate Resilient City Tool	-	3	5
13 Draxis UP2030 Decision Support System	5	5	6
14 Air quality monitoring and forecasting service	1	5	8
15 Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs -InVEST	5	8	9
16 Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis solution	?	?	?
17 Urban Building/Transport Energy Model	3	3	5
18 BIM module & Building LCA assessment module	5	5	5
19 MIRA solution for Cities as Digital Twins	6	6	6
20 Circular Urban Planning	2	2	5
21 Integrated Digital Twin Framework	-	3	5
22 Modular Urban Farm	8	8	8
23 GeoKey/Community Maps	9	9	9
24 Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping	1	2	5
25 Learning and Action Alliances method	-	-	-
26 Neutrality Story Maps	-	3	6
27 Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities	4	4	7
28 City Resilience Framework	9	9	9
29 Spatial Justice Package - Benchmarking tools	2	3	5
30 Hydroflows	5	6	7

4.2 City-Tool Mapping Overview

Table 36. City Prototype - tool mapping

Cities	Tools/Solutions
Belfast	Community Maps Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping Child and Youth Friendly Urban Design Method Community Maps
Budapest	Community Maps Circular Urban Planning Storytelling for Participatory Exchange
Granollers	Resilience Assessment Framework Data-Driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design Neutrality Story Maps
Istanbul	Urban Building/ Transport Energy Model PV Integrated Urban Furniture Integrated Digital Twin Framework
Lisbon	Air Quality Monitoring Tools for Measurements in the Urban Water Cycle Circular Urban Planning
Milan	Ecosystem Services Assessment- InVEST Cities Resilience Framework
Münster	Climate Proofing Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping Neutrality Story Maps
Rotterdam	Storytelling for Participatory Exchange
Thessaloniki	UDWC Methodology (including facilitation and simulation toolkits) Green Economy Model
Zagreb	Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping
Rio de Janeiro	Hydroflows UDCW Methodology

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

This deliverable is the second version of the Transformative Pathway Roadmap, presenting updates on the integration of UP2030 solutions in the UP2030 cities. Each UP2030 solution is presented in a dedicated section that includes a short description and its objectives. Additionally, the city prototypes are outlined, highlighting the cities vision, the specific challenges each city aims to address, and the tools mapped to achieve this vision. Finally, an overview of the integration and interoperability plan is provided, including milestones, timelines, and potential updates.

At this stage of the project the majority of the solutions are mapped into cities' prototypes and the effort is allocated to the implementation of the first version of the prototypes by February 2025 (Mil. 13 on M26). The integration effort will continue until the final version of the city prototypes, by M33.

The Transformative Pathways Roadmap is a living document, with information updated as the UP2030 project progresses and when significant changes occur. It builds on D3.1, and an updated final version, D3.3, will be delivered in M36. By that point, the final prototypes will be presented in detail as the roadmap reaches its conclusion.

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